

Participation of the Community in Management of Tourist in the Village of Torosiaje Sub District Popayato District of Pohuwato Gorontalo Province

Bambang Suharto, Lis M. Yapanto
State University of Gorontalo

Abstract:- This research aims to be implemented in Torosiaje village, Popayato District, Kabupa ten Pohuwato Gorontalo Province. The research method used is qualitative method with descriptive design. Primary data collection is done through questionnaires and in-depth interviews and documentation. While the secondary data collection is done through literature tracking or interviews with related institutions such as village heads, heads of hamlets, and community leaders and society Torosiaje. The results showed that the contribution of Torosiaje community in the management and development of marine tourism has three aspects, namely the involvement in the emotional aspect of decision making, social involvement that is maintaining the water resources as well as the member of service and comfort, supervise or monitor marine tourism and economic involvement ie manage and utilize existing marine resources.

Keywords:- community participation, maritime tourism.

I. INTRODUCTION

Indonesia is an archipelago rich in marine tourism from Sabang to Merauke. The development of tourism in Indonesia has progressed very rapidly since the government decided to rely on the tourism sector as the largest foreign exchange earner for the State. Very rapid progress occurred on the island of Bali, because Bali is very famous in the world International. Though still many areas in Indonesia and even islands that have potential to be a tourist destination. It's just that these areas have received less attention from the government (Dewi, 2013). Marine tourism area of Torosiaje village one of the marine tourism area in Pohuwato regency, Gorontalo Province. The distance from Gorontalo city to Torosiaje Village is 5 hours by road. In the great dictionary of Indonesia, (1998) in Demartoto, (2009), Participation means participating in an activity. The village of Torosiaje is a marine tourism village which of course requires community participation in the development and management of sustainable tourism. On the basis of this, this research is conducted to know how the community participation in the development of marine tourism in Torosiaje village, Popayato district, Pohuwato regency, Gorontalo province.

II. METHOD

Data collection methods used in this research is a qualitative method with descriptive design, i.e. research that gives a careful picture of individuals or groups about certain

circumstances and symptoms that occur. Where data source from this research come from primary and secondary data. Primary data collection is done through questionnaires and in-depth interviews and documentation. Questionnaires and in-depth interviews were conducted on key informants such as Village Heads, Dusun Heads, and community leaders with a total of 40 respondents. Data analysis is data obtained in the field of both primary data and secondary data presented by using qualitative approach in the form of exposure which then narrated in accordance with the problems in research (Dalimunthe, 2007).

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Characteristics of respondents who dominate in the age range 31-40 years as much as 37% and the least is the range of age less than 20 years as much as 5%. Seseoa rang considered mature in terms of thinking and more experienced in the age range 31-40 years (Suroso et al, 2014). And the type of job respondents are Fisherman 85%, Traders 10% and PN S 5%. According to Udin (2010), someone has a job that is considered prestigious (civil servants, private) will be socially respected and regarded as a figure or intellectual by most societies, so that in any community development activity the person will always get the main place in every stage of the existing development process.

Torosiaje village is one of the nautical attractions with main attraction is coral reef ecosystem and reef fish. Community participation in marine tourism development in Torosiaje Village is as follows:

A. Participation Inngamb Peilan Keputusan

Based on interviews conducted with Torosiaje people, it was found that not all Torosiaje villagers involved in the decision were those who were community leaders, traditional leaders, representatives of the village government, and representatives of the general public. The village of Torosiaje as a maritime tourism village also establishes a community of tourism awareness that aims to reduce the impact of damage caused by unsustainable capture of the environment such as using bombs and others that can damage will be sanctioned by the community based on the prevailing rules. According to Timothy, (1999) in Sahawi, (2015) there are two perspectives in viewing local community participation in the decision-making process by accommodating the wishes and goals of local communities in development as well as their ability to absorb tourism benefits. Communities in the development area should be encouraged to identify their own aims of driving tourism

development to improve the economy of local communities. Based on the results of interviews in Torosiaje Village community and field observations indicate that the supporting facilities for marine tourism activities have not been feasible for visitors or not yet adequate. Existing facilities are aids from the tourism government of Pohuwato Regency which is a means of lodging, electricity, and water.

B. Partisipasi In Maintaining Water Resources

The people of Torosiaje village are known to be fishing fishermen who often use bombs, but now the level of awareness and participation of the community is evident with the supervision of the aquatic environment that is the formation of a community watchdog group that helps and participates in maintaining the aquatic Environment in order to remain beautiful as a famous tourism destination in Pohuwato District. Marine Tourism in Torosiaje Village will grow as the community participates in training on tourism and community skills training, to increase community knowledge. Interviews indicate that Torosiaje villagers have participated in training conducted by the government, although these activities only include some representatives from the community. One of the training that is done is the skill training of the community that is training to make the craft for souvenirs typical of Torosiaje village which the materials are easy to do because utilizing existing natural resources such as shells, sand, and others.

C. Participation Provides Services And Security To Tourists

According to Khalik (2014), Comfort and security are becoming very important conditions in the tourism industry. Environmental factors that deserve. obey the inconvenience and insecurity of tourists is the management of parking. Structuring and management of parking in the village Torosiaje including safe and comfortable because it has been built r parking place for tourists. And local people are involved in maintaining the security and comfort of visitors or tourists who come.

D. Community Participation in managing marine tourism in Pohuwato regency.

Based on the results of the interviews, it was found that before the existence of electricity and the means of transportation (boat) of local tourists who came to conduct activities wisatanya using small boats, one additional income of fishermen in transportation services for visitors Torosiaje village as a village of marine tourism area in Pohuwato district. Marine Tourism in the village of Torosiaje Pohuwato District is growing as the community participates in participating in training on community skills. To increase knowledge. The results of the interviews indicate that Torosiaje villagers have participated in training carried out by the government, although these activities only included some representatives from the community.

E. Participation In Overseeing or monitoring Tourism activities

According to Dewi (2013), various tourism development policies are aimed at improving and assisting the community in increasing community participation in coral reef areas in marine tourism activities. At a certain level there has been a process of improving the views,

insight, knowledge, awareness and behaviour of the community towards marine tourism development program.

Participation of Torosiaje Village Community in supervising and monitoring marine tourism activities is shown by the enthusiasm of the community when there are activities of tourists visiting to do marine tourism such as to the nearest islands, diving, in the village of Torosiaje.

Villagers of Torosiaje especially those who are members of the watchdog group, without being asked to be a *guide* for tourists. According to Dalimun the (2007), people can participate directly to develop environmental conservation as well as a deep understanding of the ins and outs of coastal ecosystems so as to establish awareness of how to behave in order to preserve coastal areas in the present and future.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of this study it can be concluded that community participation in tourism development in Torosiaje village Popaya to District Pohuwato Regency Gorontalo Province is as follows :

- Emotional involvement in decision making
- Involvement from the social side of maintaining water resources, providing services and security, supervise, and monitor marine tourism
- Economic involvement of managing and utilizing marine resources is marine tourism and ole-ole craftsmen group (souvenir).

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